

SUPPRESSION OF INTERLAMINAR CRACK IN UD-CFRP CONTAINING FIBRE DISCONTINUITY USING POLYAMIDE MESH

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ABSTRACT

A fiber discontinuity in fibre reinforced composite laminates may act as a source of stress concentration that induces damage onset. A mesh made of thermoplastic polyamide (PA) as an interlayer is inserted between fiber continuous and discontinuous plies in order to suppress an interlaminar cracking as a second damage mode in unidirectional CFRP laminates that contain centred fiber discontinuity. It is experimentally shown that by inserting PA mesh the onset stress of the interlaminar crack increased significantly. The end notched flexure (ENF) testing using unidirectional CFRP laminates with PA mesh inserted demonstrates that the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness $G_{IIc} = 1.91 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ can be achieved; this should be compared to 1.30 kJ/m^2 without PA mesh. It is also shown that the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness $G_{IIc} = 3.67 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ which is related to the second critical load, not the first one, during ENF testing should be applied to the prediction of the crack onset stress by using an analysis model that incorporates energy release rate by the crack growth.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced composites such as CFRPs recently have been applied to not only aerospace but also automobile structures due to their high specific strength and stiffness. Because of their fibre direction dependent properties, continuous fibres should be oriented in the same direction with the predicted load direction in structural designs. When one fabricates complex composite geometries by laminating unidirectional prepregs, for example, some precuts or slits are introduced to them to achieve appropriate fibre directions and to trace the shape without wrinkles. These prepreg cuts can reduce wastes of prepregs and then lead to low cost in CFRP manufacturing. In this regard it is significant for wide application of CFRP to understand the strength and damage behaviour in the CFRP laminates containing fibre discontinuities introduced by prepreg cuttings.

To date, some researchers have evaluated effect of the prepreg cuttings in tapered composite structures on their mechanical properties and damage behaviour. For instance, Fish and Lee predicted delamination onset stress in the structure based on maximum shear stress criteria [1]. Her represented the ply drop-off part where delamination and fracture can be easily taken place by a finite element model, and attempted to analyse the singular stress field in that part [2]. Unidirectional arrayed chopped strands (UACS), which is a sheet made by introducing slits into a conventional prepreg, have been proposed by Taketa et al. [3]. They successfully fabricate complexly shaped composite components with layered structure maintained. Most of these reports, however, dealt with the multiple fibre discontinuity parts and/or off-axis loading since they assumed the fibre discontinuity in real

structures. So far, there have been few papers available that basically investigate the effect of pre-preg-cut as fibre discontinuity on the mechanical properties in unidirectional CFRP laminates.

Nakatani et al. have evaluated relations between mechanical properties and damage behaviour and predicted damage onset stress by incorporating energy release rate in an analytical model for unidirectional CFRP laminates $[0_8]$ containing fibre discontinuities in 2, 4 and 6 plies that locates in centre of the laminate [4,5]. They revealed that two main damage modes were observed under tensile loading; a crack initiated in the resin rich part that formed at the edge of fibre discontinuity then this crack proceeded in interlaminar between the continuous and discontinuous plies as interlaminar delamination. Nakatani et al. also have successfully improved the onset stress of the interlaminar crack using interlaminar-toughened CFRP laminates (T800S/3900-2B) where thermoplastic particles about 20 micro meters in diameter are dispersed in their interlaminar to suppress interlaminar delamination under such as out-of-plane impact loading [6].

A mesh made of thermoplastic polyamide (PA) that shows good fracture toughness is inserted between fibre continuous and discontinuous plies as an interlayer in this paper to suppress the interlaminar cracking as the second damage mode. It is expected that one can achieve the crack suppression mechanism that can be observed in the interlaminar-toughened CFRP laminates at a relatively low cost. Here, the increases of onset stress of the interlaminar cracking between fibre continuous and discontinuous plies are experimentally presented, and also evaluated in terms of interlaminar fracture toughness and analytical prediction. The effects of the inserted PA mesh on the interlaminar crack growth behaviour are discussed also by comparing the experimental results using the interlaminar-toughened CFRP laminates.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Unidirectional CFRP laminates were fabricated using 8 plies of carbon/epoxy prepregs (T700SC/2592, Toray) with autoclave. The fibre discontinuities were introduced by placing prepregs that were pre-cut perpendicular to the fiber direction edge to edge while making clearance gaps as narrow as possible before moulding. Fibre discontinuities were formed in 2, 4 and 6 plies out of 8 plies in the centre of laminates, then PA mesh were inserted between fibre continuous and discontinuous plies as shown in Fig. 1. The unidirectional CFRP laminates without PA mesh were also tested for comparison. In Fig. 2 one can see appearance of the PA mesh applied here (N-NO175T, NBC Meshtec Inc.) and properties of the mesh are shown in Table 1.

After autoclave moulding the unidirectional CFRP laminates were cut into 200 mm \times 10 mm coupons then GFRP tabs were adhered both ends for gripping and strain gages were attached on just above the fibre discontinuity and also on the position 20 mm away from the fibre discontinuity to obtain tensile specimens as shown in Fig. 3. Tensile testing was carried out using a universal load frame (Autograph AG-I, Shimadzu Corp.) under crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. During the tensile

Figure 1: Schematic of fibre discontinuity and PA mesh inserted.

Figure 1: Photograph of the PA mesh.

Diameter of fiber [μm]	50
Thickness [μm]	87
Opening [μm]	95
Opening area [%]	43

Table 1: Properties of the PA mesh.

Figure 3: Schematic of the unidirectional CFRP laminates with centred fibre discontinuity.

testing an optical video microscope was applied to observe damage initiation and growth that can be seen in the edge surface of the specimen.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Stress-strain relations and damage behaviour

Stress-strain curves for the CFRP laminates containing fibre discontinuity are shown in Fig. 4. As for the laminates without PA mesh (Fig. 4(a)), one can see non-linear stress-strain relations just above the fibre discontinuity that are represented by solid lines until certain stress levels. Previous reports have found that these non-linear responses correspond to initiation of crack in the resin rich region at the edge of fibre discontinuity. For the specimens with PA mesh the same can be said; the initial bend or non-linear behaviour for the stress-strain curves just above the fibre discontinuity as shown in Fig. 4(b) should be related to the crack initiation in the resin rich region. From microscopic observation of edge surface of the 4-ply discontinuous specimen, one can see the crack in the resin rich region under the stress of 700 MPa regardless of whether the PA mesh is inserted (Fig. 5). It should be noted that suppression of this crack by inserting the PA mesh is not expected here.

As for the stress-strain relations 20 mm away from the fibre discontinuity that are represented by dashed line, one can see discontinuous behaviours where strain increased sharply after linear responses for the laminates without PA mesh. These discontinuous responses have already found to be attributed to the onset of interlaminar crack between fibre continuous and discontinuous plies. So the interlaminar crack onset that is interested in this paper can be detected by these discontinuous responses or the sharp increase in the strain 20 mm away from fibre discontinuity. Fig. 6(a) shows microscopic observation results of the 4-ply discontinuous specimen under stress of 774 MPa that is

just after the sharp increase of the strain. One can see that the crack which is initiated in the resin rich region proceeded into the interlaminar between fibre continuous and discontinuous plies. Compared to this, stress of discontinuous responses in the stress-strain curves i.e. the interlaminar crack onset increased significantly or disappeared by inserting the PA mesh. Microscopic observation of 4-ply discontinuous specimen with PA mesh also revealed that the interlaminar crack was not induced even if the tensile stress or 1400 MPa was applied as shown in Fig. 6(b). Since some specimens did not show the onset of interlaminar crack it seems that the crack onset stress is comparable with the fracture stress of the laminates.

The stresses of the discontinuous responses in stress-strain relations as the interlaminar crack onset are plotted as a function of number of discontinuous plies in Fig. 7. For the specimens that did not show the interlaminar crack by inserting PA mesh their fracture stresses are adopted here. This figure clearly indicates that the interlaminar crack onset stress was significantly improved for any number of discontinuous plies by inserting PA mesh. Results for the interlaminar-toughened CFRP laminates (T800S/3900-2B, Toray) obtained by a similar testing [6] are also plotted in this figure to compare the onset stress. Though one should consider the difference in the strength of carbon fibre (T700SC and

Figure 4: Stress-strain curves of the unidirectional CFRP laminates containing fibre discontinuity (a) w/o PA mesh and (b) with PA mesh.

Figure 5: Microscopic observation of crack in the resin rich region.

Figure 6: Microscopic observation of the interlaminar crack between the fibre continuous and discontinuous plies.

Figure 7: Interlaminar crack onset stress as a function of number of discontinuous plies.

T800S), inserting PA mesh enable us to achieve higher onset stress of the interlaminar crack compared to the interlaminar-toughened CFRP laminates.

3.2 End notched flexure tests

The interlaminar crack growth should depend on the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness between the fibre continuous and discontinuous plies. End notched flexure (ENF) testing was carried out to obtain changes in mode II interlaminar fracture toughness by inserting the PA mesh. According to the JIS K7086 24-ply unidirectional laminates of $[0_{12}/0_{12}]$ (without PA mesh) and $[0_{12}/PA/0_{12}]$ (PA mesh inserted) with initial crack introduced before testing were subjected to three-point bending.

Fig. 8 shows load-displacement relations during the three-point bending. Higher load can be seen before load-drop for the laminates with the PA mesh inserted (Fig.8 (b)). The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness as mode II critical energy release rate G_{IIc} can be given as

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9a_1^2 P_c^2 C_1}{2B(2L^3 + 3a_1^3)} \quad (1)$$

where P_c is critical load, C_1 is compliance at critical load, B is width of the specimen and L is distance from center to supporter. Estimated crack length at critical load a_1 can be obtained by,

Figure 8: Load-displacement curves during the ENF testing.

Materials	G_{IIC} [kJ/m ²]
T700SC/2592 w/o PA mesh	1.30
T700SC/2592 with PA mesh	1.91
T800S/3900-2B Ref.[7]	1.64

Table 2: Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness.

Figure 9: Fracture surface of the ENF test specimen.

$$a_1 = \left[\frac{C_1}{C_0} a_0^3 + \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{C_1}{C_0} - 1 \right) L^3 \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (2)$$

where a_0 is initial crack length and C_0 is compliance for initial linear elastic part. Care must be taken when selecting the point of critical load P_c . The cross point of the load-displacement curve and 5% offset line P_5 before load drop, or local maximum load point P_{max} when this can be seen first before the cross point is adopted for the critical load. For the laminates without the mesh determination of P_c is simple here since $P_c = P_5 = P_{max}$. By inserting the PA mesh the local maximum can be seen in higher load then $P_c = P_5$. Obtained mode II interlaminar fracture toughness is shown in Table 2 with G_{IIC} of the interlaminar toughened CFRP laminates (T800S/3900-2B) [7]. From this table it is found that by inserting the PA mesh as interlayer the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness $G_{IIC}=1.91$ kJ/m² was achieved; this should be compared to 1.30 kJ/m² without PA mesh. It should be also noted that $G_{IIC}=1.91$ kJ/m² is superior to that of 1.64 kJ/m² for the interlaminar toughened CFRP laminates. Fig. 9 shows fracture surface of the specimen after ENF test. It is observed that the interlaminar crack propagated between the one side of the PA mesh and the CFRP ply by tearing off the epoxy resin that was filled in opening of the mesh. Large area of interface between the PA mesh and epoxy resin that shows debonding as interlaminar crack can enable strain energy to be released without rapid crack growth, then apparent mode II interlaminar fracture toughness can be improved.

4 PREDICTION OF INTERLAMINAR CRACK ONSET STRESS

4.1 Analytical model

Previous studies have suggested an analytical model for energy release rate by considering force equilibrium before and after the onset of the interlaminar crack, and then successfully predicted the crack onset stress by applying experimentally obtained or assumed mode II fracture toughness of the material [5]. Same analysis was applied here to see if the proposed model can also predict the onset stress of the interlaminar crack even if the PA mesh is inserted to the CFRP laminates to obtain improved G_{IIC} values as evaluated above.

As shown in Fig.10 a quarter of the laminate was modeled in 2-dimension. The crack in the resin rich region and the interlaminar crack with its length of a as red dashed line are already presented. Shaded part is assumed not to be subjected to a load since this part is surrounded by the cracks. As can

be seen in the figure, E_1 , E_2 , t_1 and t_2 are elastic moduli and thicknesses of the fibre continuous and discontinuous plies, respectively. Here, $E_1 = E_2 = 130$ GPa and $t_1 = t_2 = 0.6$ mm. For $0 < x < a$ and $a < x < L$, which are subscripted as "i" and "ii" respectively, strains ε_i and ε_{ii} can be written as

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{\sigma_i}{E_1} = \frac{P}{E_1 t_1} = \frac{\sigma(t_1 + t_2)}{E_1 t_1} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ii} = \frac{\sigma_{ii}}{E_1} = \frac{P}{E_1(t_1 + t_2)} = \frac{\sigma(t_1 + t_2)}{E_1(t_1 + t_2)} = \frac{\sigma}{E_1} \quad (4)$$

where σ is applied stress in x direction and P is load. Displacement in entire model $\delta(a)$ is then,

$$\delta(a) = \varepsilon_i a + \varepsilon_{ii}(L - a) = \left(\frac{t_2}{t_1} a + L\right) \frac{\sigma}{E_1} \quad (5)$$

By the crack growth, where crack length increases from a to $a + da$ at a moment the displacement and load reach $(\delta(a), P)$, the displacement is assumed to increase to $\delta(a + da)$ under constant load P . Change in potential energy $d\Pi$ by this interlaminar crack growth can be expressed by area oab, which is calculated by subtracting area obd from oabd as shown in Fig. 11 then,

$$d\Pi = \frac{P}{2} (\delta(a + da) - \delta(a)) \quad (6)$$

Now energy release rate G by the interlaminar crack growth can be written as,

$$G = -\frac{d\Pi}{da} = \frac{\sigma_0^2 t_2 (t_1 + t_2)}{2E_1 t_1} \quad (7)$$

From Eq. (7) one can obtain the stress of the crack growth σ_0 as,

Figure 10: Analytical model to predict the interlaminar crack onset stress.

Figure 11: Load-displacement relation with crack onset.

$$\sigma_0 = \sqrt{\frac{2E_1 t_1 G_c}{t_2(t_1 + t_2)}} \quad (8)$$

where G_c is critical energy release rate. Since it was observed that onset of the interlaminar crack corresponds to propagation of the crack originated in the resin rich region, the stress of crack growth of Eq. (8) can be compared to the experimental onset stress of the interlaminar crack.

4.2 Predicted stress of the interlaminar crack onset

By applying mode II interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IIc} shown in Table 2 to the critical energy release rate G_c in Eq. (8) one can predict relations between the onset stress of the interlaminar crack and number of discontinuous plies out of 8 plies as shown in Fig. 12. Predicted stress agreed well with the experimental results for the laminates without PA mesh as depicted as solid blue curve. Compared to this, onset stress was predicted to be much lower when the PA mesh was inserted to the laminates (red dotted line in Fig. 12). The interlaminar toughened CFRP laminates showed similar results where the crack onset stress cannot be predicted by the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness $G_{IIc}=1.64$ kJ/m².

Since variable that can be parameter in the prediction here is only the critical energy release rate, relations between crack growth behaviour and load-displacement curves during the ENF testing should be evaluated in detail. By carefully observing Fig. 6(b) one can see that relatively small cracks already initiated near the corner of the resin rich region. However these cracks were not detected by change in strain as described in section 3.1 because strain gages are attached 20 mm away from the center of the specimens. The crack growth detected in the experiment is the massive one that leads to the rupture of the laminates. Again, there are two step of crack growth; the first is the small crack near the resin rich region and the second is the large crack just before the fracture.

In the load-displacement curve during the ENF testing for the laminates with the PA mesh (Fig.8 (b)) one can see a small bend at (3.4 mm, 780 N) and the load drop (4.6 m, 930 N). These two should be responsible for the first small crack and the second massive crack that can be detected by strain gage, respectively. In section 3.2 load at the small bend was adopted as critical load P_c to obtain G_{IIc} since the 5% offset line intersected with the curve exactly at the bend. So $G_{IIc}=1.91$ kJ/m² shown in Table 2 may correspond to the energy released by the first small crack. When the mode II fracture toughness G_{IIc} is calculated by adopting the local maximum load P_{max} at the load drop point as the second critical load $P_{c'}$, one can obtain $G_{IIc'}=3.67$ kJ/m².

By using $G_{IIc'}=3.67$ kJ/m² the crack onset stresses were successfully predicted for the CFRP

Figure 12: Predicted interlaminar crack onset stress compared to the experimental results.

laminates with PA mesh though some differences still remained as shown by red solid line in Fig. 12. In the same manner the crack onset stresses in the interlaminar toughened CFRP laminates are also predicted by applying $G_{IIc} = 2.80 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ that is assumed here not the mode II fracture toughness $G_{IIc} = 1.64 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ that one can find in some literatures. Change in the energy release rate at the crack tip as a function of crack length also known as the crack growth resistance curve or the R-curve should be discussed to improve the prediction.

5 CONCLUSIONS

To suppress the initiation and growth of the interlaminar crack between the fibre continuous and discontinuous plies as the second damage mode in the unidirectional CFRP laminates those contain fibre discontinuities in the centre of them, the mesh of thermoplastic polyamide (PA) was inserted as an interlayer. It is experimentally shown by tensile testing that a sharp increase in strain at 20 mm away from the fibre discontinuity which corresponds to the interlaminar crack onset can be seen at higher stress level or does not occur until rupture of the laminate by inserting the PA mesh. The end notched flexure (ENF) tests demonstrated that mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of $G_{IIc} = 1.91 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, compared to $G_{IIc} = 1.30 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ without PA mesh, was achieved. An analytical model that incorporates energy release rate by the interlaminar crack growth was suggested to predict the crack onset stress. The model successfully predicted the crack onset stress when the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness $G_{IIc} = 3.67 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, obtained by adopting the second critical load during the ENF testing, was taken to the calculation. The massive crack growth just before the rupture should be related to G_{IIc} for the unidirectional CFRP laminates containing fibre discontinuity with PA mesh inserted.

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